

CYCLOPES - Fighting Cybercrime – Law Enforcement Practitioners’ Network

Deliverable 6.10 Website and social media channels (LinkedIn, Twitter) Public

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Summary

This document, Deliverable 6.10, relates to the development and launching of the CYCLOPES website and social media channels - providing detailed information about their structures and how they are to be used to support the project's communication and dissemination efforts.

Introduction

The CYCLOPES website and social media channels are critical for supporting the ongoing interactions with the CYCLOPES network and related stakeholders. The channels provide interfaces to conduct communication, dissemination and exploitation activities within the project.

The aim is to promote CYCLOPES objectives, progress and results to a wide range of audiences and the relevant stakeholders. Likewise, the project's communication team aims to establish strong connections and relations with key actors that are vital for the project to run efficiently and achieve its goals. Therefore, the channels will also be used to share useful and appropriate content concerning current affairs and the changing trends within the cyber domain. This will include - but will not be limited to:

- latest news and trends;
- highlighting interesting findings and actions from connected projects, networks and initiatives;
- sharing industry specific technologies and innovations that can support practitioners their duties;
- raising awareness of events and gatherings that supplement the project's goals and complement the abilities of EU law enforcement to counter cybercrime.

To ensure the website provides a user-friendly and informative environment, the team has kept the approach simple.

Social media is currently restricted to two channels – Twitter and LinkedIn - that the team believes best support the audience and objectives of the project.

CYCLOPES website

The project website uses the domain <https://www.cyclopes-project.eu> and is also compatible with Mobiles and Tablets.

When designing the website, the team kept the layout simple, but also modern. Besides, due to the technical nature of the project's topic – the goal was to create something attractive and interesting to those that are technically-minded.

To achieve this, the communication team defined a list of page-specific requirements and functionalities. However, these were to be developed on top of a system supporting the following high-level requirements:

High-Level Requirements

Figure 1 CYCLOPES Website Requirements

The project website structure

To achieve the simple, but modern design, the structure of the CYCLOPES website is divided into on 5 main pages, namely:

- Home
- About (Project Overview)
- News
- Events
- Downloads

Within the 5 central pages, the website provides information and features that allow users to **Join the Network, Contact the Project, Subscribe to the Newsletter, Engage consortium partners and associated networks.**

The architecture of the website is shown below in Figure 2.

Website Architecture

Figure 2 CYCLOPES Website Architecture

Page Requirements

To ensure that the website effectively captures the most relevant information and points concerning the project, the team used a simple brief that outlines the ‘**What, Why, When, How,** and **Where** questions’.

To translate these points into requirements, the communication team produced a list of page-specific requirements nestled under the key objectives.

For example:

News:

As CYCLOPES will be an active network with lots of activities happening in parallel, it is important that users are able to view the news articles in a clear way – regardless of the device. Plus, the content should be split into categories and easily searchable by date, topic and target audience (LEAs, Procurement, Policy Officers, Researchers, Industry, Media).

No.	Requirement	Description	Priority (MoSCoW)
1	Individual Articles	As a user, I want to read separate articles that clearly displays the category of that article, the date it was published and any specific tags (Technology, Country, Topic, etc.)	Must
2	Categories	As a user, I want to find articles in an easy way, with each post assigned to a particular category (Events, Technology, Research, etc.).	Must
3	Tags	As a user, I want to view the articles linked with relevant tags (Crime Domain - Cybercrime, Cryptocurrencies, Fraud, Drug Crime, CSAE, etc.)	Must
4	Most Read	As a user, I want to see the top 3 articles that have been read most/recommended by others. This should be displayed on each page within the news area.	Must
5	Social Sharing	As a user, I want to be able to share the article with my peers	Must
6	Article	As an admin, I want to be able to write an article and present information including text and media files	Must

Figure 3 Website List of Page-specific Requirements

The initial requirements for the first version of the website were elicited during several planning discussions and meetings. The requirements were then prioritised using the MoSCoW¹ technique. To keep costs down, and to release the first iteration of the website in a timely manner, only ‘Must Have’ and ‘Should Have’ features were developed.

As the project runs for 5-years, the design team had provisioned for future changes by using a scalable platform that can be adapted and altered to suit the specific needs of CYCLOPES as the project matures.

Graphical Interface

The design for the website follows the concept of the proposal. We live in a connected world powered by technology, and the internet and connectivity plays a significant part. Therefore, it is crucial for the project, and the cybercrime law enforcement community to reflect this.

¹ <https://www.productplan.com/glossary/moscow-prioritization/>

Figure 4 Website Home Page

Using the website, members will be able to join (top right corner) and we have an interactive map that will allow the project to highlight the members involved in the project (see Figure 5 below). It is also important for CYCLOPES to capture information about tools and solutions that can help fight the various forms of cybercrime. Therefore, it will also be easy for suppliers to get in contact with the project (as shown in Figure 6 below). Capturing data through the website will complement the efforts of WP3. Throughout the project, members of the network and interested stakeholders will be able to monitor the project's website for relevant events and activities occurring through the project and in associated projects and networks. The information will be visible on the Events page, as shown in the mock-up below (Figure 7).

Figure 5 Partner & Network Map

Figure 6 Capturing Information from Industry

Figure 7 Event Calendar Mock-up

Security

The server for the website is hosted in Poland, using the reputable provider as the hosting company. The website utilises the HTTPS protocol with a SSL certificate purchased through the same provider.

The website utilises the widely recognised WordPress Content Management System, which provides the communication team with the ability to regularly update the website content and provide users with the information on the latest events and activities of the project.

CYCLOPES Social Media (LinkedIn, Twitter)

The communication team adopts an ‘inbound marketing’² strategy and plans to keep audiences regularly updated with project activities and actions as they occur.

The content produced and generated through CYCLOPES activities will be shared through various forms. Namely, the website (News, Events, Downloads – publications, reports, articles, etc.) and social media will be used. However, the project also utilises other means of contact including Newsletters, and a variety of other engagements completed in WP5.

Social Media will be used to broadcast all of these actions, helping to drive people back to the website for further information and to interact with the network by joining or engaging in events.

The use of social media is crucial in spreading project information to a large audience. Thus, social media will be actively used during the five project period to disseminate the project’s

² Inbound Marketing relates to the activities generated by an organisation to attract interest from its audience. Inbound marketing includes content marketing, blogging, SEO, and opt-in email marketing, etc. This is the opposite of Outbound Marketing of paid adverts, cold calling, spam e-mails, etc.

ideas, actions and results. In particular, two social media accounts were created for the CYCLOPES project in July 2021:

- LinkedIn - is a social networking site for people in professional occupations or simply a social network for business. The CYCLOPES project is available on <https://www.linkedin.com/company/project-cyclopes>
- Twitter - is an online social networking service and micro blogging service that enables its users to send and read text-based messages of up to 140 characters, known as "tweets". The CYCLOPES project is available on: <https://twitter.com/projectcyclopes>

Direct links to the CYCLOPES Twitter and the LinkedIn accounts can be found on the CYCLOPES website.

Figure 8 CYCLOPES LinkedIn Profile

Figure 9 CYCLOPES Twitter Profile

Conclusion

This document provides a presentation of CYCLOPES key communication channels – the project’s website and social media.

These channels will be operated by PPHS and LAUREA respectively, while the content will be provided by all consortium partners.

Through publishing all relevant public information of the project on the official CYCLOPES website, the project gives interested parties a high-level overview of the project, including the current news and activities. Further, this allows more interaction and communication within and outside the CYCLOPES Consortium.

The content of the website and social media channels will be constantly updated, to reflect the project as it progresses and provide a user-friendly and informative environment.

More information regarding the communication and dissemination activities will follow in the upcoming deliverables:

- Branding plan and material (M4, LAU)
- Dissemination and Communication (DC) Plan (M6, LAU)
- CYCLOPES Community Building Framework and Governance model (M6 DITSS)

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